

ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF INDUSTRIAL HEAT SAVING IN VARIOUS SITUATIONS

Variny M.¹, Kšiňanová M.¹, Furda P.¹

¹ *Institute of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37, Bratislava, Slovak Republic
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk*

Abstract

Large industrial facilities and industrial clusters traditionally operate a combined heat and power unit serving as a marginal heat source. This unit can consist of either a steam Rankine cycle unit or comprise a Combined Cycle-based cogeneration unit. These distinctive designs differ by both heat to power ratio and delivered heat quality (temperature); both parameters being further impacted by the unit's operation. A change in heat quantity exported from the combined heat and power unit can thus have various impacts on cogenerated electric energy quantity and released greenhouse gas emissions. This contribution aims at elucidating this aspect of industrial heat saving projects with the goal to deliver valuable input for industrial energy managers and decision makers. Rankine and combined cycle units are modelled, providing a realistic assessment of energetic and environmental impact variability of their operation change due to the variable heat export. Greenhouse gas emissions generated in external power sources are considered as well.

Introduction

Industrial complexes and clusters tend to have complex energy supply systems, employing central and decentralised sources of energies and utilities^{1,2}, interconnected by an extensive system of pipelines. Among these, steam networks belong to most frequently studied and optimised systems³. Steam systems often comprise three or even four pressure levels that are interconnected, supplied by several sources producing steam on purpose or generating it from waste heat streams⁴. Extensive steam systems were modelled and optimised in case of steel and iron production plants⁵, petrochemical and refining enterprises⁶, pulp and paper mills⁷ as well as in other energy-intensive industries⁸. Complexity of the studies varies from assessing selected parts of the steam systems to multi-period analysis and operation optimization of whole systems^{9,10}.

Conditions securing a stable and efficient steam system operation are influenced by a multitude of factors. Transported steam quality and amount, steam system topology and technical state of pipelines, including insulation efficiency, can be counted among the most important ones¹¹. These are further impacted by plant's production load, products' structure, possible renovation and refurbishment activities, implementation of new technologies and many more, which result from the plant's development and strategical decisions made over decades¹². Any innovation activities impacting the plant's steam balance inevitably change the operation of the plant's marginal steam source – in most cases it is the central steam and power plant. To correctly assess the techno-economic dimensions of any such change, a deep understanding of the system's operation and limitations is required^{13,14}.

In this study, three distinctive case studies are considered, comprising changes in the plant's steam demand at two pressure levels and a change in condensates return to the central steam and power plant. Evaluation of each of the case studies is performed for A. a typical steam and power plant equipped with an extraction-condensing steam turbine and B. for a plant repowered by a gas turbine. The aim of this study is to highlight common trends and differences in obtained fuel consumption, CO₂ emissions and power production and to make the readers aware of system operation constraints likely to be approached in some scenarios.

Study objectives

The main goals of this study are:

- Analysis of seasonal variations of an industrial steam and power plant (ISPP), either as Rankine unit, or repowered by a gas turbine
- Evaluation of different exported heat load changes in terms of fuel consumption, power production and emitted CO₂

Combined heat and power unit description

This section provides description of the plant model scheme (displayed in Figure 1., where repowering and studied scenarios are depicted in dark grey and black). The plant combusts heavy fuel oil in a boiler, which transforms pre-heated feed water (stream no. 20) into a superheated high-pressure steam at the temperature of 530 °C. (stream no. 1). The steam flows to an extraction-condensing turbine (ECT), where the steam expands. ECT produces not only electricity but also extraction steam is produced. In repowered mode, the plant combusts natural gas with compressed air in a combustion chamber of the gas turbine. Because of the high rate of excess air used in the combustion, flue gas from the gas turbine contains high amount of unused oxygen, which created an opportunity to reuse the flue gas mixed with fresh air in combustion in the original boiler. As mentioned above, feed water used in the boiler undergoes the process of pre-heating, which takes place in the series of low temperature water heaters (by 30 °C), a degasser (by 30 °C) and high temperature water heaters (by 40 °C). Condensate loss caused by export is compensated with chemically treated water addition to a condenser.

Figure 1. Simplified schematics of thermal power plant, where streams in gaseous state are depicted by dashed lines, solid lines represent liquid streams. Legend: C = condenser; COMB CH = combustion chamber; COMP = compressor; CHTW = chemically treated water; T = turbine.

Calculation assumptions are:

- to produce at least 60 MW of electric energy (either extraction-condensing turbine (ECT) alone or ECT and gas turbine (GT) together),
- to produce high-, intermediate- and low-pressure (HP, IP, LP) extraction steam for export as well as for its own consumption,
- minimal mass flow of vapour-liquid mixture (stream no. 11) is 10 t/h
- unit is studied in two modes – non-repowered and repowered,
- calculations are divided, based on season into winter and summer production,
- gas turbine electric efficiency in repowered mode is 30%,
- gas turbine mechanic efficiency is 95%,
- lower heat value of heavy oil is 40.496 MJ/kg both in winter and summer, for natural gas it is 48.609 MJ/kg in winter and 48.931 MJ/kg in summer,

- different temperatures of humid air are considered – 4 °C (winter), 22 °C (summer) and in both cases, the air is pre-heated to 100 °C,
- relative air humidity in winter is 80 % and 65 % in summer.

In addition, three different scenarios both for repowered and non-repowered ISPP including seasonal changes in winter and summer were proposed. In Scenario 1, 50 t/h of condensate return at the temperature of 100 °C is included, Scenario 2 includes lowered consumption of low-pressure extraction steam by 30 t/h and Scenario 3 includes lowered consumption of high-pressure extraction steam by 30 t/h.

Mathematical model

In this section, the most important steps of calculation and the mathematical model development is described. Basis of the calculation is to assemble material and enthalpic balances of ISPP units as shown in equation (1) and equation (2).

$$\sum \dot{m}_{in} = \sum \dot{m}_{out} \quad (1)$$

$$\sum h_{in} \dot{m}_{in} = \sum h_{out} \dot{m}_{out} \quad (2)$$

$$(3)$$

where \dot{m} = mass flow, h = enthalpy, lower index in = inlet output, lower index out = outlet output.

Important step is to determine stream enthalpies either from literature or based on calculations. After acknowledging all assumptions mentioned in previous section, the results of mass flows for original non-repowered ISPP are obtained.

Next step is to compile material and enthalpy balances for the gas turbine based on the same principle and reconstruct the original balances for a boiler to include the flue gas from the gas turbine as a part of the combustion air. Subsequently, the results for repowered ISPP are obtained.

In addition, the electrical efficiency of ISPP and CO₂ production is calculated based on equation (3) and equation (4).

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{P_{el,total}}{Q_{fuel}} \quad (4)$$

where η_{el} = electrical efficiency of ISPP, $P_{el,total}$ = produced electricity obtained from the enthalpy balance and Q_{fuel} = total heat obtained by burning fuel.

$$\dot{m}_{CO_2} = \dot{m}_{38} \cdot w_{CO_2} \quad (5)$$

where \dot{m}_{CO_2} = mass flow of CO₂ produced in combustion, \dot{m}_{38} = mass flow of the flue gas from the boiler and w_{CO_2} = mass fraction of CO₂ produced in combustion.

Model results

This section is dedicated to the results of the mathematical model. In the Figure 2. and Figure 3., production of electric energy before and after repowering can be observed. As mentioned in the previous section, different initial states were chosen for winter and summer, which resulted in variable electricity production.

Consumption of fuel (heavy oil and natural gas separately) and CO₂ production are displayed in Table I and Table II. In this case, different values are observed for different seasons as well. When production of electric energy rises, fuel consumption and CO₂ production goes up too, which is an expected trend, but the dependency of those values is not necessarily a continual proportion.

Figure 2. Electricity production – non-repowered option

Figure 3. Electricity production – repowered option

Table I
CHP operation comparison – before repowering proposal

Non-repowered		Original		Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
		Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
Fuel consumption (t/h)	Heavy oil	29	25.3	28.16	25.13	25.99	24.24	25.99	23.42
	Natural gas	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CO ₂ production (t/h)		92.59	80.57	89.92	80.01	82.98	77.18	82.98	74.58

Table II
CHP operation comparison – repowering proposal included

Repowered		Original		Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
		Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer
Fuel consumption (t/h)	Heavy oil	25.31	19.26	24.56	19.14	22.68	18.41	22.67	17.82
	Natural gas	4.26	3.3	4.13	3.29	3.81	3.16	3.81	3.06
CO ₂ production (t/h)		92.59	92.48	70.55	89.75	70.13	82.86	67.46	82.84

Discussion and Conclusions

Data presented in Figure 2, Figure 3 and in Table I and Table II lead to the following observations:

- Winter operation requires more fuel and generates more electricity, resulting from higher exported heat load, compared to summer operation.
- Repowered ISPP fulfills the required power production and heat export with less CO₂ emissions than the non-repowered one.
- Condition of minimum 60 MW power production causes an adequate increase in condensing power production in summer if exported heat load decreases (Scenarios 2 and 3); low pressure steam export decrease leads to less fuel saving than the same decrease in high pressure steam export.
- Smallest fuel saving and CO₂ emissions decrease is observed in case of condensates return (Scenario 1 = internal heat consumption decrease).
- Repowered ISPP performs better than the non-repowered one, in all scenarios, but the observed trends are similar. Extra power from the gas turbine decreases condensing power production and contributes to cleaner power production and overall CO₂ emissions decrease.

This demonstrates the need for individual assessment of heat saving projects in industry when an ISPP operation change is involved.

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